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KEY GROWTH DRIVERS AND BARRIERS TO ADOPTION OF E-PAYMENTS: A REVIEW

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Abstract

New monetary wants have been emerged due to e-commerce which was lacking with standard payment systems. The presence of this e-commerce has initiated different payment tools or mechanisms for completing the business transactions through internet. Therefore, the stakeholders came up with completely new strategies for electronic payments. The e-payments in India have witnessed an exponential growth in last few years, at the same time faced some challenges. In this article, a modest attempt is made to critically analyse key drivers of exponential growth of e-payments in India, as well as key barriers to adoption of e-payments in India. The article is based on exploratory research and secondary data. The data was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available. This article provides an original insight of key growth drivers and barriers to adoption of e-payments in India.

Keywords: *Financial transactions, E-commerce, Digital currency, Indian economy, Growth drivers, Barriers, E-payments.*

1. Introduction

New monetary wants have been emerged due to e-commerce which was lacking with standard payment systems. The presence of this e-commerce has initiated different payment tools or mechanisms for completing the business transactions through internet. Therefore, the stakeholders came up with completely new strategies for electronic payments. Recognising this, just about all interested parties square measure exploring numerous forms of the electronic payment system and problems encompassing electronic payment system and digital currency.

Usually, e-payment systems could be categorised into On-line Electronic Money System, On-line MasterCard Payment, Electronic Cheque, and Cards based mostly Electronic Payment System. Every payment system has its blessings and downsides for the purchasers and merchants. Security, convenience, cost, anonymity, acceptableness, traceability, and control are some basis mandates of these new payment systems. Most of the banks have started following e-commerce supporting the e-payment system for sustaining in the hyper-competitive market.

Though Indian economy is considered as a cash-driven economy, however, it is not so far away in adopting e-payment services in banking as well as a retail sector (Roy, 2015).

The financial system is considered as a real backbone of any economy. A reliable and transparent financial system is a must for handling an increasing number of monetary transactions of the economy. Here, the financial system means, banks as well as non-bank financial institutions that are offering different types of financial services to their targeted customers. Fund transfer, as well as financial clearing, are considered two prominently important services as compared to other services of the payment system. The payment system is a key role player in enhancing the business growth, improving the financial intelligibility and supporting the reforms of the sector. The attitude and behaviour of people or customers of new payment system have been changing drastically from last two decades. The major reasons for the same are following:

1. **Increased either volume or value of transaction:** Not only the numbers but also the value of the transactions are increasing as the people are considering their financial matter most important. Because of this new phenomenon, there is a rapid growth in the activities of the financial market can be noticed around the globe and the payment generated by such activity.
2. **Technological enhancement:** From last 20 years there's an unbelievable technological improvement in banking and money sector. It's owing to the advancement of data and communication technology and big growth of net. As a result, money establishments and shoppers each have the flexibility and therefore the resource to manoeuvre funds abundant quicker through the system, at a lower value.
3. **Effect of globalisation:** As an outcome of the globalisation, many businesses have started to overcome geographical boundaries. As a result, a lot of money transactions are flowing across the countries. The corporate that has the aptitude to contour its payment mechanism is ready to trim prices and therefore succeed competitive advantage. This will be attainable solely in cross-nation payment.

Globalisation and financial revolution came with some drastic changes in developing countries in various aspects. Some of the notable changes are: new opportunities of trading and investments, changes in the consumers taste and preferences, increase in the demands of international products. Technological advancements have also played a critical role in making the world borderless. Improved communication and information technology have also provided unbelievable chances in the world economy, with the help of the Internet, countries are connected digitally. Electronic money is the outcome product of this digital convergence and also proved as electronic replacement of cash. The idea of electronic payment for trading in goods and services is not new to the world. Several schemes were offered to promote the electronic payment or payment through a computer network in late 1970's as well as early 1980's. Aristotle (384 – 322 B.C.) said that “everything must be assessed by money; for this enables men always to exchange their services and so makes society possible.”

2. Objectives of the study

In this article, an attempt is made:

- To critically analyse key drivers of exponential growth of e-payments.
- To critically analyse key barriers to adoption of e-payments.

3. Methodology

The article is based on exploratory research and secondary data. The data was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available. This article provides an original insight of key growth drivers and challenges in Indian retail industry.

4. Key drivers of the exponential growth of e-payments

4.1. Mobile trajectory

India is holding a 2nd position in the world with over 100 corers of mobile subscribers (Shah *et al.* 2016). From which the customer who uses a smartphone is near about 24 corers and by year 2020 users are estimated to increase over 52 corers.

4.2. The online network

The online network of India is day by day increasing even in the isolated parts of the country, with the 3G and 4G sharpness network. The National Optical Fibre Network (NOFN) action taken by Digital India to provide high-speed Internet service to cover 2.5 lakh Gram Panchayats across rural India. In the current scenario, there are 30 corers of users from rural areas who are accessing the internet from their mobile handsets, and it is estimated that there will be an increase in adoption of data-enabled devices in these areas. By 2020 the percentage of using mobile handsets with data enabled devices will raise near about 50% with respect to this year which will be around 65 corers.

4.3. Digital transformation in banking

Over the years, electronic or digital transactions are taking place and the growth rate is about 50% year-over-year, with the support of ATM transactions growth rate of 15%. And the bank branch-based transactions are reduced by almost 7% in the year 2015 as compared to the year 2014 (Shah *et al.* 2016).

4.4. Supporting regulatory environment

In the today's world, there are many changes taken place in the payment method. The technology and the customer expectations are constantly changing with rapid growth and that is being recognised by the governing body and the concerned regulators. However, this is just the start and requires more development in this area to make more conducive electronic payments for the success of business in this country. Given below are the key regulatory steps that are now a day's authorised as an electronic payment in India:

- **KYC tranquility for teeny transactions:** According to the RBI instructions there is no need for the customers to undertake the process of KYC for up to INR 10, 000 per month on prepaid instruments transactions. The instructions made the customers easy to download the wallet of their choice and use them for transactions without the

requirement of documentation, photograph etc. By this, the requirement traditional banking service is being fulfilled.

- **Exemption from Two-Factor Authentication (2FA):** According to the instructions of RBI (May, 2015), the incorporation of two-factor authentication (2FA) the settlements made in Indian debit/credit cards, notwithstanding of transaction values.

This is required for the customer's security, it is also risky, and the difficulties in the payment process, the number of transactions fails and drops-off. The different mobile wallet requires customers to undertake 2FA process only while adding fund in the wallet from other bank tools. Further, the mobile wallets have limits on the transaction value and help to increase the security of details which the customer provides.

Figure 1: India is becoming a digital country

(Source: Shah *et al.* 2016)

- **Aadhaar Making KYC easier:** With the unique identification number is given by Aadhaar has made the KYC process very easy. By linking the mobile number with the Aadhaar card digitally this process now becomes very easy. Due to Jan Dhan Yojna initiative taken by the government near about 27 Corer accounts has been opened. This made the banking sector strong with high security and the biometric authentication a reality.
- **Unified Payments Interface (UPI):** The Unified Payments Interface is developed by NPCI (National Payments Corporation of India) is a system through which the customers can manage their payments and the transactions. The Unified Payments Interface changed the entire services pattern from the transaction like Immediate Payment Service (IMPS), Automated Clearing House (ACH) to RuPay into one stage. This allows the perfect interoperability and the possibility unlocking of multiple solutions. The built-in

software will provide the access to all the payment service providers; it can be banks, FinTechs, Payment bank etc. This provides the users with the flexible accessing bank account with any device and payment service providers which are connected to the UPI set-up. From which the customers will be able to choose the User-Id in any format like mobile number, Aadhaar ID, email ID etc. And they expect us to improve the service and the user experience and provide simple payment solutions. There is also the requirement of UPI payments for the peer payments, person to merchant payments and business to business payments.

- **Bharat Bill Payment System (BBOPS):** Bill payments are the important elements of retail payment transactions. Cash and cheque payments are now the main elements for the billers from their point of view. According to customers, the systems do not provide the proper access to the bill desk in the digital payment transactions. And they are owned and operated by NPCI, BBPS is expected to be as an 'Integrated Bill Payment System' that is able to make use of information, approachable, cost-effective and allowing multiple payment modes.

4.5. Emergence of nextgen payment service providers

It has been seen that significant transactions are done in India last 3-4 years. The competitive online payment landscape in India now reach Telco's, banks, wallet companies, e-commerce/tech firms and in the near future, payment banks.

- **Bank-led:** In the past, the banking sectors launched the mobile payments applications with the integrated bill payment solutions. However, the use of mobile application and wallets are unsafe or fearless for the customers for the bill payments. Now, the all banks have started their own mobile applications and wallets with high security in to the customers like, SBI – State Bank Anywhere, HDFC Bank – Mobile Banking, iMobile – ICICI Mobile Banking, BOI BTM – Bank of India Mobile Banking, Axis Mobile, CANMOBILE – Canara Bank, M-Connect – Bank of Baroda, PNB mBanking. All these applications and the wallets are not required to have a bank account they can be the existing users to log on using their internet/mobile banking identity. The banks have lots of existing customers as compared to independent m-wallet forms so need to do customer's acquisition.
- **Telco-led:** Vodafone and Airtel launched m-payments solutions, VODAFONE M-Pesa and Airtel Money respectively for their selected own customers. And the others like Idea Money form Idea Cellular, mRUPEE by TATA and Jio-Money by Reliance is some telco-led-payment solution launched to make the payments simultaneously as per the customer convenience. The solutions were initially Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) based on using non-digital savvy more than online payment. The main uses of such applications were largely for mobile recharges and payments.
- **Prepaid wallets:** In 2009-10, 26 prepaid payments instrument licensed (PPI) was issued RBI. PPI licensed issuers can now issue semi-closed wallets that validate payments without 2F Authentication. As the outcome, 2 types of PPI emerged.

- **Mobile wallets:** M-Wallets are mostly used for bill payments and recharges through their application based a stored value account, which is funded by credit/debit card or net-banking like Paytm, MobilKwik, Freecharge and Citrus Pay etc. The companies approved by VC funding spent in large amount on customer acquisitions through marketing initiatives. Shortly, the diversified existing business model to create on the customer base through expansion of service. There are tie-ups with radio cabs (Paytm-Uber, Paytm-Ola), offline POS payment such as (M-swip), payment at fuel stations and educational institutions etc.
- **Prepaid Cards:** The customers who are unaware of the online platform are provided with the solution by the companies' agents like Oxigen, Itz Cash, Suvidha and GI Tech. Payments and railway ticket booking is the main usage in this case. Some of PPI are obtained by tech firms like e-commerce, radio cabs, and entertainment booking to offer in-house wallet solutions. For example, Snapdeal acquired Freecharge, Flipkart acquired FxMart to offer Flipkart money and Amazon acquired Emvantage. While Ola offers Ola Money, Bookmyshow too has its own wallet app to service customers. By looking towards the growth, other companies have registered for such licenses with the total count of PPI licenses increasing to 46 licenses in 2016.
- **Payment Banks:** The activities of payment banks include approval of DD (Demand Draft) up to 1lakh rupees per customer, giving ATM/debit card, offering payment and payment service, performing as Business Correspondent (BC) to other banks and issuance of Mutual Funds, insurance services etc. These types of banks cannot accept any advance/ lone activities like credit card receives NRI deposits or become a "virtual" bank. As per RBI's announce of driving financial involvements and permits high & low-value transactions so that lessens the vulnerability of cash. RBI provided an approval to 11 organisations to set-up payment banks in 2015. These organisations include telecom Players like Airtel, Vodafone, Uninor, and Idea Reliance Jio, tech-centric payment players like Paytm, freecharge, next billion focused players like NSDL, Fino, India Post and NBFCs like Mahindra Finance, Cholamandalam. In addition to the economic model for payment banks are demanding, stated that they cannot earn a lending income of high rates of interest in launch because of demand of investing customer deposits in government securities. Some of the licenses such as Cholamandalalm. Uninor and Mahindra Finance have already repaid there in proposition consent to RBI.

4.6. Enhanced customer experience

In today's world, peoples in India are getting used to digital network, and are also demanding for providing the same facility of the digital network by their financial service providers. This includes fearless access to bank accounts and payments, coupled with rewards, loyalty, and offers.

- **Superior and Seamless customer experience:** In this year there is seen a huge trend of online shopping in India. The easy and convenient way of buying from e-commerce entrants like Amazon, Flipkart Snapdeal etc and get almost everything sitting online at

one place at home is too good to resist. Also, the youth are in favour of using Ola/Uber rides instead of normal cabs to avoid the inconvenience of paying the exact amount by cash. Paytm's alliance with Uber and Ola Money by Ola have performed "the get in-get out" circumstances in the taxi industry. Therefore, payments are the background activities while the center of attraction is on making users experience seamless. In the billing industry, there are multiple steps involved in payment applications i.e. logging into the app, registration of the user, payment registration, 2FA and the final payment. In addition to mobile banking and Net banking, they have high-security instructions in logging out if the user is inactive for long period, etc.

- **Attracting customers with offer and discounts:** The mobile wallets are still new to the customers in India, so the companies are offering great deals, discount and offer to customers and increasing awareness. Paytm offered 8000 Rs. as a discount on iPhones and iPads in 2015 and Freecharge offered cashback offer on minimum bill payments. Ola and Uber also have offered 50% cash back on the previous bill payments. In the meantime, MobiKwik and Paytm are also known for the offers giving their products, providing credit to the wallet and the discount coupons of partner merchant's outlets. All the offers and discounts given to the customers helps to encourage them in using the applications to buy the products and make payments.

4.7. Rise in adoption of online payments

The quantity of mobile transactions done in 2012-2013 is similar to the mobile wallets and Prepaid Payment Instrument (PPI) deals completed in the next 4 years span. Near about 747 million deals were occurred in the year 2015-2016 with the help of mobile wallets and prepaid cards combined, whereas the transactions made by mobile banking were about 390 million (Shah *et al.* 2016). So it is being said that, most of the transactions done through a mobile wallet, are less than average ticket size of INR 620 and on average mobile banking transactions are 10,400 Rs. pre transactions, notching up a total annual deals value is of 4000 million. In terms of how many customers do the transactions through online banking versus how many customers use mobile wallets, already the mobile wallet customer has exceeded the online banking users (60 Million). The amount of wallet users is tripled before the number of credit cards provided in the country (24 million in 2015-16) (Shah *et al.* 2016). If we check the growth rate in internet keyword search in the past six years from July 2010 to Jun 2016, we will see that keyword holds the word "pay" raise by 18X since July 2010. These were taken as substitutes for the requirement for digital payment. Search keywords for "pay/wallet/money transfer" increased much faster by 3 times speedily in last year, as compared to search keywords for industries like e-commerce, credit, and insurance.

Figure 2: Comparative analysis of prepaid instrument transaction and mbanking transaction

(Source: Shah *et al.* 2016)

5. Key barriers to adoption of e-payments

5.1. Habit to use cash

In today's world also the Indian peoples prefer to make cash payments instead of online payments. According to the survey, almost 68% of the population uses cash payments (Shah *et al.* 2016). Due to these, the national and international e-commerce industries included cash on delivery payments for the Indian customers. The cause behind this strategy is that people are having a problem to handle the cash, and the peoples are happy with the way it trades and are not excited about the change to handle money easily as it is fixed in their day to day life.

Figure 3: Key barriers to adoption of e-payments

(Source: Shah *et al.* 2016)

5.2. Complexity of usage

Out of total percentage, half the customers do not use the online transactions application due to; they find it too difficult for them. In fact, one-third of non-users didn't know how to use the application, while one-fifth of non-user think not to use as well it is useless to try because it's too complicated for them. As online transaction marks the miscellaneous users and merchant segments for across the value linked application blueprint need to evaluate that the solution must build for the base communicated judiciously. Actually, if we differentiate, the cash is always a satisfactory option for the transaction because it's more convenient and preferably and more acceptable to the people and easy to use. Revolution in transaction essentially raising day by day as it takes the simplicity of the application.

5.3. A perceived lack of compelling value proposition

Most of the people didn't use the online transaction because they could not find it safe either they do not understand the application, easily or in fact unknowingly they keep themselves away from the benefits they may have. Even consumer didn't hear or talk about the online transaction since they find themselves unsafe from it, and it lacks a ratio of digital payments. Since consumer has a tendency that they didn't find themselves safe for the application they use, so adoption ratio might get affected. Payment Service Providers shall provide the essential key points for an online transaction that consumer may captivate and use it. Rather than the customer may be beneficial for the use, so he could use the application without the hesitation. For that, Providers must interact with the customer as well as they have to educate and communicate the benefits clearly.

5.4. Inconvenience, low reach and possibility of making mistake arresting usage

The reasons behind which lacks the usage of online banking are that users may disrupt of remembering the password, insufficient balance, possibility of technical or human mistake during a transaction etc. To overcome all this difficulties customer service providers shall have been giving the details to customers, for the proper ways to use the online transaction whatever might be important to them. For example, implement biometric authentication instead of multiple username and password, acquisition and unification of under the system would increase the affirmation of people towards the online transaction they do. Furthermore, auto sweep feature can also help in addressing low account balance and the maintenance of required minimum balance in the online transaction account.

5.5. Security, identity theft, and fraud are big barriers in India

The primary research in India shows that the hidden charges and frauds are not genuine online transaction instruments. In facts, the two customers who have never used online transactions and afraid of the frauds happening.

- The dissimilar universal market, security, privacy, and fraud aren't head of mind related.
- 75% of merchants believe that digital will increase and accelerate future sales (Shah *et al.* 2016).

The research also remarked that most merchants have an obstacle with the small change, with some literally paying money to obtain the change to manage their day to day work.

Figure 4: Reasons for stopping usage of e-payment

(Source: Shah *et al.* 2016)

Figure 5: Payment instrument mix of countries

(Source: Shah *et al.* 2016)

6. Conclusion

The e-payments in India have witnessed an exponential growth in last few years, at the same time faced some challenges. Key drivers to the exponential growth of the e-payments in India are mobile trajectory, the online network, digital transformation in banking, supporting regulatory environment (e.g. KYC tranquility for teeny transactions, exemption from Two-Factor Authentication, Aadhaar making KYC easier, Unified Payments Interface, Bharat Bill Payment System), emergence of next generation payment service providers (e.g. bank-led, telco-led, prepaid wallets, mobile wallets, prepaid cards, payment banks), enhanced customer experience (e.g. superior and seamless customer experience, attracting customers with offer and discounts, rise in adoption of online payments).

Key barriers to adoption of e-payments are habit to use cash, complexity of usage of e-payment modes, a perceived lack of compelling value proposition, inconvenience in using e-payments, low reach and possibility of making mistake arresting usage, security, identity theft, and fraud.

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